

Digital Dilemmas: AI and the Invisible Biases

An interactive exhibition by
MAMMOth

university of
 groningen

jantina tammes school
of digital society, technology
& artificial intelligence

rijksuniversiteit
 groningen

MAMMOth

What is MAMMOth?

MAMMOth is a 3-year research project aiming to make artificial intelligence (AI) fairer and less biased. It is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Program.

Why?

In today's world, artificial intelligence (AI) is widely used, for example:

1. Movie and music recommendations on streaming services such as Netflix and Spotify.
2. Assistants such as Siri and Alexa that help with everyday tasks.
3. Facial recognition at passport checks at airports.
4. Analyzing traffic patterns to improve urban planning.

But, if these systems are biased, they can lead to unfair results and increase inequality.

MAMMOth's mission is to ensure that AI treats everyone fairly, regardless of gender, race and other characteristics.

You can help!

MAMMOth believes in collective action. Together we make AI fairer, which in turn makes for a fairer society.

So you can contribute to this:

- By sharing your opinion during this exhibition.
- By being a critical user of AI.
- By demanding transparency and honesty in the AI tools you use.

Who are we?

Goya Buitenhuis

Hello, I am Goya and I designed and executed this exhibition, under the supervision of Dagmar Heeg. I did this as part of the master's degree in Science Communication and Education at the RUG.

Of course I would love to hear what you thought of this exhibition! Should you enjoy sharing your opinion, feel free to call/message to: +31615100341 or email me at g.y.buitenhuis@student.rug.nl.

Who are we?

Dagmar Heeg

Hi, I'm Dagmar and I work at the Centre for Learning and Teaching at the RUG. I do research on AI literacy. On behalf of MAMMOth, I develop educational materials to make people aware of the ethical dilemmas surrounding AI.

Would you like to give feedback on our materials, or even help develop them? You can! Sign up using the QR code below.

Want to learn more? Check out:

Research RTL facial
recognition (in dutch)

Algorithmic justice
league

Documentary:
Coded Bias

Thank you

During the making of this exhibition, many people helped me. Without them this project would not have been possible.

I would like to thank them:

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MAMMOth

Multi-Attribute, Multimodal Bias Mitigation in AI Systems

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